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A reliable procedure to estimate the rupture propagation directions from source directivity: the 2016-2018 Central Italy seismic sequence

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Figures S1 to S2: Supplementary Figures showing details of the analysis and results.

Introduction

This Supplementary Information includes the analysis of the results variability using different EGF, and for each seismic events considered in this study, the directivity index D_{index} versus the azimuth of the rupture propagation direction, the map of the seismic events occurred in a radius of 5 km and in a time interval of 2 days before and after the target event, and the cumulative number of the logarithm of the energy in the forward, backward, and fault-orthogonal directions.

Figure S1. Analysis of the variability of the results obtained using different EGF. (a) D_{index} versus the seismic event numbered as shown in Table S3; (b) Azi_{evt} of the rupture propagation direction versus the seismic event numbered as shown in Table S3.

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(a)

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(b)

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(c)

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(d)

(e)

Figure S2 (a-e) For each analyzed seismic event: on the left, D_{ij} versus the azimuth of the rupture propagation direction; in the middle, map of the seismic events occurred in a radius of 5 km and in a time interval of 2 days before and after the target event; on the right, cumulative number of the logarithm of the energy in the forward, backward, and fault-orthogonal directions. In the map and in

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the right plot the seismic events are colored based on the geographic position respect the target event: in red for the forward, in black for the backward, in blue e cyan in the orthogonal position, respectively.